

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION ON DIRECT INJECTION DIESEL ENGINE FUELLED WITH Al₂O₃ NANOPARTICLES DISPERSED BIODIESEL BLEND

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Abstract- The present analysis focuses on the vibration level of a direct injection compression ignition engine running on a biodiesel blend (BD20) containing scattered Al₂O₃ nanoparticles. In this experiment, a combination of biodiesel from Jatropha seed oil and Al₂O₃ nanoparticles were used. The Al₂O₃ nanoparticles were considered as a fuel additive. The concentration of nanoparticles in BD20 was adjusted to 60 and 80 parts per million (ppm), respectively. All fuels were tested in a direct injection diesel engine with an injection pressure of 240 bar to determine the degree of engine vibration. The nanoparticle additives in BD20 have shown remarkable effectiveness in vibration control with nano fuel. The BD20 + 80 Al₂O₃ fuel exhibited the lowest root mean square (RMS) velocity compared to the other remaining fuels. The vibration intensity of BD20 + 80 Al₂O₃ at 240 bar was measured to be 0.375 m/s.

Key Words- Jatropha myrtle ester, Aluminum oxide, vibration, parts per million.

I. INTRODUCTION

Due to the increasing demand for energy, the depletion of fossil fuels, and strict emission regulations, science is forced to look for alternative fuels such as biodiesel for diesel engines. These fuels aim to bridge the gap between energy demand and sources in the automotive industry [1, 2]. Moreover, from an economic perspective, India spends around INR 80,000 crore annually on the procurement of petrol alone. The use of domestically produced biodiesel fuels could reduce expenditures and possibly boost the national economy [3]. Biodiesel has the characteristics of being easily accessible, naturally decomposing, easily transportable, not harmful to living organisms, and able to be replicated.

Various non-edible seeds, such as pongamia, jatropha, mahua and castor bean, are used to produce biodiesel. These non-edible oil crops are classified as second-generation feedstocks because they are inexpensive and can be easily grown in many regions of the world [4,5]. Transesterification is a very practical and effective technology that can be used to convert any non-edible oil into a substance that has similar properties to diesel fuel. Abul Kalam Hossain and Abdul Hussain [9] use esterification and transesterification methods to produce Jatropha biodiesel. Cerium oxide (CeO₂) and aluminum oxide (Al₂O₃) were added to this biodiesel at concentrations of 50 parts per million (ppm) and 100 ppm, respectively. The properties of the nanoparticles were examined and compared with those of diesel fuel. Jatropha biodiesel blended with 100 ppm Al₂O₃ nanoparticles was chosen for the engine tests, mainly because of its higher calorific value and good integration. S.N. Shreenivasan and C. Chinnasamy [10] used waste plastic oil as a source of biodiesel along with the addition of aluminum oxide (Al₂O₃) nanoparticles. The tests were carried out on a single-cylinder four-stroke diesel engine with an adjustable compression ratio under various loads. The Brake Thermal Efficiency (BTE) increased and the Brake Specific Fuel Consumption (BSFC) as well as the carbon monoxide (CO) and hydrocarbon (HC) emissions decreased. A.P. Senthil Kumar et al [11] used ultrasound to combine aluminum oxide (Al₂O₃) and cerium oxide (CeO₂) nanoparticles with diesel fuel. They then

conducted experiments on a variable compression ratio (VCR) engine. The values for carbon monoxide (CO) and nitrogen oxide (NO) decreases, as the proportion of cerium oxide nanoparticles increases, the HC value decreases.

In addition, extensive studies are being carried out to investigate the effects of different fuels on vibration and noise levels. In recent years, several researchers have conducted studies on the performance of gasoline engines running on alcohol-based fuels such as ethanol. Nevertheless, the effects of vibration and noise on the internal combustion engine result in low fuel consumption. Engine vibration is the oscillation or fluctuation of the mechanical system or the state of equilibrium within the engine. Uncontrolled engine vibrations can endanger the safety of occupants [12-13]. In addition, excessive vibrations also lead to noise in the vehicle. Engine vibrations are caused by various factors such as engine speed, load, oil viscosity and fuel properties.

The engine combustion optimization method involves analyzing changes in vibration, load, ignition and ignition duration to determine the most efficient combustion settings. This method was developed to improve fuel consumption, pollutants and noise levels. Therefore, various efforts have been made to reduce the characteristics of engine vibration. A study was conducted to investigate the effects of vibration and noise characteristics caused by diesel petrodiesel fuel [14]. This experiment was conducted on a four-cylinder engine that was converted from natural gas to gasoline fuel. The test results can mitigate the vibration and noise and minimize the carbon monoxide and hydrocarbon emissions. also [15] conducted a study on the vibration and noise caused by Karanja biodiesel fuel. The 20% biodiesel combination has the strongest engine combustion noise. Karanja biodiesel at a concentration of 20% has the strongest vibration intensity. These factors are the result of shortened combustion duration, increased heat release rate and prolonged ignition delay. a study was conducted in [16] on the effects of ethanol-gasoline blended fuels on vibration and noise characteristics. The experimental results show that both vibration and noise increase at 1500 and 2500 rpm. The increase is attributed to the increased oxygen content and latent heat of the ethanol-gasoline fuel combination compared to other fuel blends. Previous studies have investigated the effects of different vibration and noise characteristics of diesel engines when using a combination of diesel and biodiesel [17]. The experiment was conducted on compression-ignition engines with four cylinders and four strokes. There is also a close correlation between the vibrations caused by the natural gas fuel and the combustion pressure of the engine [18]. The results of the study indicate that the vibrations generated exceed the mechanical vibration levels. A study was conducted to investigate the vibration and noise levels of genset engines running on a mixture of diesel and n-butanol [19-21]. The test results indicate that vibration and noise levels improve slightly at low engine loads. However, when the engine load is increased, vibration and noise increase. The correlation between vibration and noise and engine combustion is quite significant. In the study, an assessment of engine vibration was made by testing a gasoline engine with a fuel mixture of methanol and gasoline [22].

II. EXPERIMENTAL APPARATUS AND PROCEDURE

An experiment was conducted with a TAF-1 (Kirloskar) compression-ignition engine, a water-cooled single-cylinder engine with direct injection. Figure 1 shows the schematic diagram of the experimental setup. Table 1 contains a comprehensive description of the specific parameters and characteristics of the experimental test equipment. The tests were carried out at maximum load (100% load) and an injection

pressure of 240 bar at a constant speed of 1500 rpm. Once the laser light beam had reached a stable state, it was aimed at a specific point on the engine body. The Vibrosoft program is able to capture these signals and convert them into a vibration signature.

Fig 1: schematic view of experimental setup

TABLE 1: ENGINE SPECIFICATIONS

Constraint	Depiction
Make	Kirloskar, TAF-1
Brake power (kW)	3.5
Bore × Stroke	87.5 mm×110 mm
Engine speed (rpm)	1500
No. of cylinders	1
Compression ratio	17.5
Injection pressure (bar)	240 bar
vibration analysis software	Vibrosoft-20
Vibration device	LDV, USB based and dual channel

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2 shows the temporal variation of the vibration. The observations show that BD20 has a lower vibration intensity compared to conventional diesel fuel. Due to its excellent ignition properties, such as higher cetane number and significant oxygen availability, biodiesel promotes smooth and efficient fuel combustion [23, 26, 27].

Fig 2: Variation of Velocity with respect to Time

Therefore, the complete combustion of a fuel takes place and successfully minimizes the occurrence of knocking. This is because the tendency to knock creates the powerful effect of vibrations. The vibrations emanating from the engine are largely due to the uneven inertial forces and the lateral pressure on the cylinder walls caused by knocking. The contribution of vibrations from fuel combustion is one of the main sources [23, 24, 27, 28]. The Al_2O_3 nanoparticle dispersion BD20 has also shown lower vibration levels. The addition of nanoparticles could promote combustion due to the better thermal conductivity and additional heat transfer due to the larger surface area to volume ratio in Al_2O_3 nanoparticles [25, 29, 30]. This promotes complete ignition and thus reduces knocking. Similarly, when Al_2O_3 nanoparticles were used in BD20, a significant reduction in the tendency to vibrate was observed. The greatest reduction in vibration was observed at a higher injection pressure of 240 bar. The root mean square (RMS) velocities at a pressure of 240 bar were 0.435 m/s, 0.353 m/s, 0.329 m/s and 0.238 m/s, respectively.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study focuses on measuring the vibration acceleration rate of combustion diesel engines with full load at 240 bar injection pressure and different fuel blends. Based on the results of testing of fuel blends. The intensity of vibration (RMS velocity) of BD20 and Al_2O_3 nanoparticle dispersed BD20 were observed minor as the regular diesel. The comparative drop in vibration was continued at 240 bar injection pressure for BD20 and nano-fuels. Among all the fuels, BD20 + 80 Al_2O_3 was shown a more reduction in RMS velocity (0.238 m/s) at 240 bar injection pressure.

Based on the above conclusion, the jatropha seed oil biodiesel blend (BD20) with Al_2O_3 nanoparticle can be fueled as an alternative fuel in a compression ignition engine with no further changes. Besides, future investigations could be carried out for the assessment of performance, combustion, and exhaust emission studies of compression ignition engine by changing the injection pressure and compression ratios as well. In addition, the proportion of Al_2O_3 nanoparticle can be varied in BD20 and tested further

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